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STATUS AND POTENTIAL OF LOW CARBON SCENARIOS IN HAI PHONG CITY-VIETNAM

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Annotation: One of the important solutions to reduce dependence and fossil fuels is to develop and implement low carbon scenarios. The content of this article is to assess the situation and potential of applying a low carbon scenario in Hai Phong city.

Keywords: Low carbon scenario

1. Make a problem

The world is facing many risks and challenges due to the use of fossil fuels. The excessive emission of greenhouse gases from fossil fuel use is causing environmental changes such as greenhouse effect, climate change, threatening the lives of billions of people on Earth.

To reduce dependence on fossil fuels, the world has made radical moves from the current economy to a low-carbon economy. Low carbon access varies from country to country, depending on the potential, opportunities and capabilities of each country.

Hai Phong is the third largest city in Vietnam, so the successful implementation of low-carbon development in Hai Phong contributes significantly to the implementation of low-carbon development in Vietnam.

2. Current status of low carbon implementation in Hai Phong city

Hai Phong is a coastal city located in the northeast of Vietnam. According to the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD) announced on July 5, 2007, Hai Phong is one of the 10 cities in the world most threatened by climate change in the next 70 years. Recently, climate change in Hai Phong city is becoming more and more obvious. These changes have a direct impact on the lives of the people and the development of the city [1-3].

Adaptation and mitigation of damage caused by climate change have become strategic tasks of Vietnam in general and Hai Phong city in particular in the process of construction and development. Identifying response to climate change as an important task, in 2014 Hai Phong City People's Committee issued an Action Plan to implement the National Strategy on Green Growth for the period 2014-2020, an action plan to respond to climate change and sea level rise of Hai Phong city by 2025 [3-5]. The goal of the action plan is to improve the ability to respond to climate change, and to avoid and minimize the negative impacts of climate change. climate change, ensure sustainable development, protect people's lives; At the same time, 46 projects and priority tasks have been proposed for implementation. Currently, the city is also implementing the project to update the Action Plan to respond to climate change and sea level rise in Hai Phong city to 2025. This will be the basis for departments, branches and localities. in the city area to review, supplement, adjust and integrate climate change factors into strategic programs and socio-economic development plans of branches and localities; At the same time, it is consistent with the scenario of climate change and sea level rise for Vietnam, updated version 2016.

With the support of the Japanese Ministry of Environment and the Japan International Cooperation Agency (JICA), Hai Phong city and Kitakyushu city have jointly researched and formulated the «Plan to promote green growth in Hai Phong city». «. The study was completed in May 2015, divided into 07 implementation areas including Waste, Energy, Transport, Cat Ba Island, Water Supply and Sewerage and Stormwater Drainage, Environmental Protection, Simultaneous Green Growth propose to implement 15 specific pilot projects for each field. The goal of the «Plan to promote green growth in Hai Phong city» is to reduce greenhouse gas emissions into the environment, towards a green port city.

Since 2015, Hai Phong City People's Committee, through the Department of Natural Resources and Environment, has coordinated with the Institute of Strategy and Policy on Natural Resources and Environment – Ministry of Natural Resources and Environment, Asia Integrated Model Group -Pacific AIM in Japan (including Kyoto University Japan, Ritsumeikan University, National Institute of Environmental Research of Japan – NIES, Institute of Global Environmental Strategy – IGES and Mizuho Research and Information Institute Japan) to study and develop a

Low Carbon Scenario for Hai Phong City. Scenario with support to calculate initial CO₂ emission reduction for energy use sectors including: Industry, Commerce, Transport and Residential.

The city's emission reduction target is in line with the national GHG emission reduction target expressed in the National Green Growth Strategy (reduced by 10-20 % in the 2030CM scenario) and in the Green Growth Strategy. expected nationally determined contribution to Vietnam's climate change (8-25 %).

3. Forecast of greenhouse gas emissions based on socio-economic scenario of Hai Phong city

On the basis of strategies and planning: National strategy on green growth (approved by the Prime Minister in Decision No. 1393/QD-TTg dated September 25, 2012), National action plan on green growth. Green growth (approved by the Prime Minister in Decision No. 403/QD-TTg dated March 20, 2014) and orientation of a green port city (Conclusion No. 72-KL/TW of the Central Committee), Hai The Department issued an Action Plan for the implementation of the City's Green Growth Strategy (Decision No. 1463/QD-UBND) in July 2014. With the target in the report Expected Contribution to be Self-Determined by the Country. of Vietnam (INDCs) under the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) is to reduce its total emissions by 8-25 % by 2030 compared to the BAU, cities in Vietnam are required to develop a Climate Change Action Plan (CCAP). This Action Plan is essential and should be integrated into the Medium and Long-term Socio-Economic Development Plan and Development Plan of each sector.

We have developed two forecast scenarios for energy consumption and CO₂ emissions in sectors such as Household, Trade-service, Transport and Industry, which are two scenarios. 2030BaU (Normal Development Scenario) and 2030CM (Mitigation Scenario). In the 2030BaU scenario, we do not set a target to reduce CO₂ emissions. This scenario reflects a relatively low level of commitment to production using environmentally friendly energy and a relatively low level of production technology conversion. In particular, the Mitigation Development Scenario is assumed to have the same level as 2013. On the other hand, in the 2030CM Scenario, low-carbon mitigation measures are introduced to assess the deflationary effect. greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. Socio-economic fields including population, industrial structure, economic growth are

covered in both scenarios. Information from various domestic sources was used to calculate the parameters for the 2013 base year. In the 2030 target year, the Extended Snapshot (ExSS) tool was used to forecast future energy consumption and CO₂ emissions in the above sectors.

Hai Phong city is forecasted with rapid growth in areas such as population, transportation demand and especially industrial activities, GHG emissions will increase to 4.01 times, from 6,675 ktCO₂eq in 2013 to 33,494 ktCO₂eq in 2030. Total GHG emission reduction is 14 %,.. Hai Phong can reduce emissions by implementing 30 projects grouped in 04 actions (Green Industry, Green Building, Efficient Energy Use and Smart Transport). Since the national GHG emission reduction target has been reflected in the National Green Growth Strategies (down from 10-20 % in the 2030CM scenario) and in Vietnam's Expected Nationally Determined Contribution Nam (8-25 %), Hai Phong hopes to achieve this target by 2030 (14 % reduction in the 2030CM scenario compared to the 2030BaU scenario).

Table 1 – GHG emissions by sector of Hai Phong city (unit: ktCO₂eq)

Field	2013		2030				2030	
	ktCO ₂ eq	%	BaU		CM		BaU/20 13	CM/Ba U
			ktCO ₂ eq	%	ktCO ₂ eq	%		
Agriculture	2	0.1	10	0.1	10	0.1	4.83	1.00
Industry	2,483	37.2	15,920	47.5	14,413	50.0	6.41	0.91
Trade in Services	221	3.3	1,470	4.4	1,170	4.1	6.64	0.80
Family	1,291	19.3	2,672	8.0	2,291	7.9	2.07	0.86
Passenger transport	604	9.1	1,634	4.9	1,350	4.7	2.70	0.83
Cargo	2,075	31.1	11,797	35.2	9,626	33.4	5.69	0.82
Total greenhouse gas emissions	6.675	100.0	33,494	100.0	28,850	100.0	5.02	0.86

Population

Table 2 presents the results of several key socio-economic indicators for the base year 2013 and the target year 2030.

In this study, the urban population in 2030 is predicted to reach 3 million people, 1.56 times higher than in 2013 according to the Hai Phong City Construction Master Plan to 2025.

Household size in 2030 is assumed to be 3 persons/household. Therefore, the total number of households is about 1 million households, an increase of 1.81 times compared to the number of households in 2013.

Table 2 – Key socio-economic indicators of Hai Phong city

	Unit	2013	2030	2030/2013
Population	People	1,925,217	3,000,000	1.56
Number of households	household	553,406	1,000,000	1.81
GDP per capita	Million VND	55	193	3.51
GDP	Billion VND	105,651	577,829	5.47
Quantity	Billion VND	282,310	1,595,478	5.65
Consumption	Billion VND	67,644	369,309	5.46
Total fixed asset spending	Billion VND	38,607	210,777	5.46
Export	Billion VND	111,247	607,360	5.46
Import	Billion VND	111,847	609,616	5.45
Passenger transport demand	million people.km	10,236	22,490	2.20
Freight transport needs	million tons.km	8,470	48,158	5.69

Transportation needs

Due to population growth and industrial activities, in 2030 the transport demand of Hai Phong city is also forecasted to increase rapidly from 10,236 to 22,490 million persons per km for passenger transport and increase from 8,470 to 48,158 million tons per kilometer for freight compared to 2013.

In passenger transport, there is a rapid increase in the demand for cars, up nearly 8.25 times. In the 2030BaU scenario, the transportation needs of cars and motorbikes are the same. According to the forecast of Hai Phong City Department of Transport, the contribution of public transport such as trip buses will increase from 0.26 % in 2013 to 10 % in the 2030BaU scenario and reach 15 % in the future. scenario 2030CM. In the field of freight transport, goods are mainly transported by road, followed by river transport. According to calculations, the market share of vehicles for freight transport in 2013 and 2030 is the same, in which road transport still leads, contributing to 91 %, and then by river transport only. contributed 8 %.

Table 3- Transport demand of Hai Phong city

	2013	2030BaU	2030CM	BaU/2013	CM/BaU
Passenger transport (million people/km)	10,236	22,490	22,453	2.20	1.00
Walk	84	130	130	1.56	1.00
Bicycle	988	1,540	1,540	1.56	1.00
Motorbike	7,908	9,232	8,367	1.17	0.91
Car	1,204	9,932	9,932	8.25	1.00
Bus	52	1,655	2,483	31.68	1.50
Cargo (million tons/km)	8,470	48,158	48,158	5.69	1.00
Road	7,174	40,789	40,789	5.69	1.00
River Road	1,296	7,369	7,369	5.69	1.00

Source: Hai Phong City Department of Transport, 2016.

Economy

According to the forecast of the Department of Planning and Investment of Hai Phong city, by 2030 the GDP growth rate (gross domestic product) will be up to 10.5 %/year. Gross domestic product (GDP) in 2030 increased by 3.51 times compared to 2013. The trade – service sector still dominates, contributing to 55.4 % of the city's economic structure. coming is the industrial sector contributing about 37.4 %.

Industrial output is forecasted to increase 5.65 times in 2030 (VND 1,595,478 billion) compared to 2013 (VND 282,310 billion).

GDP per capita of Hai Phong in 2013 is about 55 million VND, will increase nearly 3.51 times in 2030. GDP per capita in 2030 is estimated to reach 193 million VND due to growth rapid growth of GDP (10.5 % per year).

In 2030, in the field of import and export, the city is expected to increase 5.46 times for exports and 5.45 times for imports compared to 2013. Consumption also increases from 67,644 billion VND in 2013 to to VND 369,309 billion in 2030, of which the main consumption is from households for industrial products and services; while government consumption focuses on science, technology, and other services.

Energy consumption

In 2030, final energy consumption is forecasted to increase rapidly to 9,308 thousand tons of oil equivalent, while in 2013 it is only 1904 thousand tons of oil equivalent. In the 2030CM scenario, the final energy consumption is about 8,090,000 tons of oil equivalent.

Energy intensity as a percentage of GDP decreased from 18.0 tons of oil equivalent/billion VND in 2013 to 16.1 tons of oil equivalent/billion VND in the 2030BaU scenario and 14.0 tons of oil equivalent/billion VND in the 2030BaU scenario. 2030CM scenario because the growth rate of energy consumption is slower than the rapid growth of GDP.

Table 4 – Relationship between energy use and greenhouse gas emissions

	2013	2030BaU	2030CM
Energy intensity (toe/billion VND)	18.0	16.1	14.0
GHG emissions per GDP (tCO ₂ eq/billion VND)	63.2	58.0	49.9
GHG emissions per capita (tCO ₂ eq/person)	3.5	11.2	9.6
Final Energy Consumption (ktoe)	1,904	9,308	8,090
GHG emissions (ktCO ₂ eq)	6,675	33,494	28,850

Greenhouse gas emissions

To forecast greenhouse gas emissions, we use two approaches: top-down and bottom-up. The top-down approach is used to forecast socio-economic activities and energy demand and greenhouse gas emissions from a macro perspective. A bottom-up approach is used to develop technological assumptions (technology popularity and energy savings rates under proposed climate change projects to forecast deflation). greenhouse gas emissions of projects).

In the 2030BaU scenario, total GHG emissions are projected to be about 33.5 million tons of CO₂, increasing fivefold compared to 2013 (6.7 million tons of CO₂).

In the 2030 BaU scenario, the main source of emissions is industry (about 15.7 million tons of CO₂), followed by the transportation industry (about 13.4 million tons of CO₂), households (about 2.7 million tons of CO₂). and the trade-service sector (about 1.5 million tons of CO₂).

GHG emissions in the 2030CM scenario are predicted to decrease by 14 % compared to the 2030 BaU scenario. The contribution to GHG emission reduction is shown in Figure 3.

From Table 4 it is easy to see that in 2013 the city's per capita GHG emissions were only about 3.5 tons of CO₂, although in the BaU scenario, the emissions are estimated to increase to 11.2 tons of CO₂. In the 2030CM scenario, emissions can be reduced to 9.6 tons CO₂ equivalent.

As for the intensity of greenhouse gas emissions, in 2013, the intensity of greenhouse gas emissions is forecasted to be about 62.3 tons of CO₂ equivalent/ billion VND. In the 2030BaU scenario, the emission intensity reduced to 58.0 tons of CO₂ equivalent/billion VND due to the main contribution from the third industry in the GPD. In the 2030CM scenario regarding the implementation of projects and actions, it has been calculated that the intensity of greenhouse gas emissions will be about 49.9 tons of CO₂ equivalent/billion VND.

4. Potential application of low carbon scenario for Hai Phong city

4.1. Green industry

Action 1 covers low-carbon projects related to the promotion of energy efficient appliances and fuel conversion in the industrial sector. The total GHG emission reduction of this action is 1,477 ktCO₂eq. Energy saving in factories is also one of the main projects of action 1, assuming

technology diffusion of 30 %, it will reduce GHG emissions by about 602 ktCO₂eq.

4.2. Green building

Low-carbon projects that refer to the widespread adoption of low-energy buildings and homes are grouped in this act. In action 2, emissions are expected to be reduced to 262 ktCO₂eq. Encouraging the use of solar water heaters can reduce KHN emissions the most in this action. The technology prevalence in this project is hypothesized to be 20 %. Energy demand in households and high-rise buildings is tending to be more economical thanks to energy management systems and the installation of insulating glass.

4.3. Use energy sparingly and efficiently

In Action 3, GHG emissions are expected to be reduced by 363 ktCO₂eq, including projects that encourage the use of energy efficient devices such as air conditioners, lighting in households and high-rise buildings. ; encourage the use of energy efficient appliances such as refrigerators and other appliances. This contributes to the largest reduction in CO₂ emissions, about 172 ktCO₂eq. Replacing traditional lighting with energy efficient lamps such as LEDs in households and high-rise buildings will also significantly reduce CO₂ emissions.

4.4. Smart traffic

This action includes a variety of passenger and freight-related projects such as the promotion of energy efficient vehicles, the transition to public transport and the deployment of electric buses. Projects for freight transport such as promoting the use of fuel-efficient trucks, which will significantly reduce greenhouse gas emissions due to the relatively high greenhouse gas emissions from freight transport.

5. Conclusion

Hai Phong has all the elements needed to successfully implement a low carbon scenario. Following a low carbon scenario will ensure a sustainable future for the port city.

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